

The Digital Afterlife: An Inquiry into Digital Remains

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ABSTRACT

As a work in progress, this paper will demonstrate the disturbing ambiguity concerning what happens to the colossal amount of *digital remains*—the photos, videos, and messages left behind by deceased internet users (Lingel, 2013) on online platforms. By describing the current state of scholarly inquiry into how digital remains are conceptualized, this paper will provide a preamble exploration of issues and ethical implications related to information privacy, digital dignity, and the potential commodification of digital remains (Karppi, 2013; Öhman & Floridi, 2017). This discussion aims to demonstrate that the data of the dead should be handled with dignity as a category of information that deserves protection. This protection is not for implicit harms against the information of the deceased, per se, but for the implications that any violation of this dignity imposes on surviving family and the larger community of mourners. Without effective policies and regulations that provide guidelines for service providers and internet users, the dead are not afforded rights to their privacy or digital dignity, nor is their postmortem data protected.

KEYWORDS

Digital remains; informational privacy; posthumous personhood; social media platforms; digital dignity

INTRODUCTION

Whether we realize it or not, the digital platforms we engage with every day are brimming with the digital traces of the dead. For example, Facebook alone is estimated to have 50 million profiles of deceased users (Harrison, 2018). As the world's largest digital graveyard (Ambrosino, 2016; Harrison, 2018) Facebook is transforming into an ad-hoc memorial space for the deceased and a communal place of mourning for the bereaved (Massimi & Charise, 2009). The subject of how Facebook is managing the colossal amount of *digital remains*—the photos, videos, and messages left behind by the deceased on the platform (Lingel, 2013)—is gaining more widespread attention, most especially when something goes wrong in its handling.

Facebook is just one platform within the newly emerging *digital death industry*—an umbrella term for digital infrastructures that offer services such as online memorialization pages; virtual funerals and graves (e.g., the “Find a Grave” webpage; the use of platforms like Facebook to live stream funerals); posthumous messaging platforms (e.g., Afternote; SafeBeyond); chatbots and avatars (e.g., Replika’s the Roman Mazurenko digital avatar); and virtual reality (Öhman & Floridi 2017; Sofka 2020). Accessible at any time and from any geographical location, mourners turn to these digital infrastructures to express their grief, experience the continued presence of the deceased through their digital remains, and find solace in the community that forms around the deceased (Sofka, 2020). Yet these digital infrastructures also have negative implications. Examples of known consequences arising within the wider discussion of online platforms and mortality include issues related to privacy, the question of access and ownership of digital remains, and the potential for commodification of user data (Kasket 2020; Öhman & Floridi 2018; Stokes 2012).

As a work in progress, this conceptual paper aims to explore the disturbing ambiguity surrounding what happens to the digital data left behind by deceased internet users on online platforms. To understand how digital remains are conceptualized, this paper presents a systematic literature review of the current scholarly inquiry and provides an introductory exploration of issues related to access and control (Kasket, 2019; Stokes, 2015), as well as ethical implications regarding information privacy, digital dignity, and the potential for commodification of digital remains (Karppi, 2013; Öhman & Floridi, 2017). Without effective policies and regulations that provide guidelines for service providers and internet users, the dead are not afforded rights to their privacy or digital dignity, nor is their postmortem data protected. I argue that protection of digital remains is necessary not only to prevent implicit harms against the information of the deceased, but also to address the implications that any violation of this dignity may have on the surviving family and larger community of mourners.

On Digital Remains

In our historical past, communicating with deceased loved ones was generally a one-way and private practice (Walter, 2015). One would find the dead resting in cemeteries and graveyards or perhaps come across a bereaved individual quietly speaking to a tombstone. The modern spiritualist movement of the nineteenth century introduced the possibility of two-way communication with the spirit realm through séances in dark rooms, Ouija boards, and mediums who fell into deep hypnotic trances and relayed messages to those present. Most often than not, if one needed to send or receive a message from the otherworldly realms, they did so intentionally by seeking out the spiritualists. And yet still, it was widely understood that the dead resided within their own abode; away from the living, accessible only through rather crude forms of communication, and making a brief visit from time to time.

Now, the dead are virtually everywhere. They reside within online cemeteries (Maciel et al., 2017; Tylec & Szegda, 2020); they make their presence felt on social media (Brubaker et al., 2013); and every now and then they may pop up in an email inbox (Stokes, 2021). Our contemporary digital era makes room for the use of technology as mediators in our Western traditional practices of mourning and memoria. The presence of digital remains is most impactful on how digital spaces are being used to commemorate and memorialize the dead (Ulguim, 2018). For instance, on Facebook the once active profile page of a user that passes on transforms into a space for the bereaved, often within minutes of their death and even, at times, before the immediate family has been notified (Hoffman et al., 2021; Marwick & Ellison, 2012). A quick “R.I.P” search on Facebook will demonstrate how the bereaved are appropriating the profile pages of the dead into a space to openly mourn and share memories of the deceased (Massimi & Charise, 2009). These spaces also allow for disenfranchised grievers (i.e., individuals whose grief may not be acknowledged or publicly supported) to come together (Walter et al., 2011). Communities and subcommunities are facilitated and allow for the formation of meaningful relationships and social connections, both online and offline (Brubaker & Hayes, 2011; Gibson, 2016; Gil-Egui et al., 2017).

For instance, when a Facebook user dies, their family can request to have their profile page memorialized. Features of a memorialized Facebook page include “Remembering [Name]” at the top of the page; maintaining content that the deceased intended on making visible; and the removal of the deceased from “People You May Know” and birthday reminders. If a bereaved individual opts to not memorialize the page of the deceased, they can request that the page be deleted; however, this is a strangely difficult process. According to the Facebook Help Desk, a request to delete an account must include documentation such as birth certificate; death certificate; power of attorney documents; and/or other forms of document(s) that Facebook may request (Facebook Help Desk 2013 as cited in Karppi 2013). Facebook does not delete its dead users; instead, it recategorizes them as *memorialized* which allows for a new way to involve them in the collaboration, participation, and production of the platform (Karppi, 2013). Once memorialized, the profile is controlled by Facebook: “After the death this power is not handed to the user or their friends and family, but to the social media platform which now preserves the account” (Karppi, 2013, p. 11). Facebook becomes the de-facto steward of its users’ digital autobiographies; their uploaded photos, videos, and messages fall into the hands of a faceless corporation with a reputation for scandal after scandal. Worse still, there is a lack of legal rights to privacy and data protection for the deceased and their digital remains: “Facebook does not have legal obligations to seek their consent nor that of their representatives before deleting, or otherwise further processing, users’ data after death” (Öhman & Aggarwal, 2020, p. 9).

On the Digital Death Industry

The advent of social media platforms on Web 2.0 introduced an industry of web-based companies that demonstrated a great interest in the data of their users. Most particularly, these companies preyed on the need for connection and sharing (Sutherland and Jarrahi, 2018; Saura et al., 2021; Varnali, 2021). Social media platforms are inherently places where users are compelled to share (John, 2017). This need for connectivity developed into “an ecosystem of connective media with a few large and many small players” (Dijck, 2013, p. 4). This new ecosystem of connective media made it easier to share thoughts, likes, photos, videos—nuanced details about what makes us who we are. For instance, in their study on hashtags on Instagram, Leaver and Highfield (2018) explored images of expectant mothers posting ultrasound photos of their unborn child as well as photos from funerals and found that, “as much as the motivation for these media involves others, the choice to capture, to post and to share is that of the active user” (Leaver & Highfield, 2018, p. 40). The practice of sharing demonstrates an evolution in how we consider our presence on the online spaces we inhabit; “It’s not just what you *do* online that matters here, however—it’s who you *are* online” (Kasket, 2019, p. 13). If we consider how many children are “born-digital” (Ulguim, 2018) and will go on to spend their lives generating content, this accumulates to lifetimes worth of digital remains. And yet for the bereaved, it may never be enough to re-read messages or revisit Facebook profiles of a deceased loved one. In recognizing this, the digital death industry is making strides to change how the bereaved memorialize and communicate with the deceased through the utilization of digital remains.

The use of technology to create or modify digital representations of the dead is not a novel idea. In fact, this phenomenon occurs regularly with deceased celebrities, and has brought attention to the possibility of their commodification. For instance, the 2021 documentary “Roadrunner,” which follows the life and career of the American celebrity chef, Anthony Bourdain, prior to his death by suicide in 2018, grossed a reported \$1.9M debut during the weekend it was released (McClintock, 2021). Although the documentary has been praised for its raw and intimate portrayal of Bourdain, it faced staunch criticism for its use of his digital voice recordings to generate an A.I. voiceover that reads the last email he sent before he took his life (Matei, 2021). Other examples include the holograms of Tupac Shakur at Coachella (2012); Audrey Hepburn singing *Moon River* in a Dove’s chocolate commercial – three decades after her death (2014); and, most recently, Robert Kardashian at Kim’s fortieth birthday party (2020). Despite having the technology to resurrect much loved celebrities (or being visited by one’s father in a hologram) *something* about the experience feels unnerving. Perhaps this is because, even after a person has died and

is no longer able to exercise their autonomy, their right to privacy is not forfeited. This applies to everyone—not just the rich and famous. Therefore, any digital information left behind by the deceased should be protected to ensure that their privacy rights are not violated.

Understanding posthumous agency requires an evaluation of how personhood is defined within a digital context (Meese et al., 2015). If we consider the *res digitalis* as the in-between (or extension, according to Floridian ethics) that encompasses all our digital traces, then there must be affordances made that protects the dignity and autonomy of this *digital self* in much the same way that there are rules (written and unwritten) that govern the treatment of the organic body (Floridi, 2016; Öhman & Floridi, 2017; Stokes, 2012). We can extend the notion of the *res digitalis* into the realm of ontology and argue that the information encompassed within the *res digitalis* is not just an extension of the body or mind, but the *informational body* of the individual given that the human body itself is increasingly a source of information (Floridi, 2016; Öhman & Floridi, 2018). A Floridian approach to the protection of human dignity posits it at the very core of the right to privacy and sets it apart from other rights, such as the right to expression or the right to property (Bawden & Robinson, 2020). And yet, human dignity in relation to informational privacy contends that “the right to privacy is beyond the individual and not something that the individual should have to work for” (Mai, 2016, p. 196), regardless of whether the individual is living or dead. As such, the informational bodies of both living and deceased online users are entitled to dignity and must be treated with the same affordances of dignity worthy of human bodies (Öhman & Floridi, 2018; Stokes, 2015).

Bereaved families often face the challenge of protecting the digital remains of their deceased loved ones from potential exploitation, hijacking, and auctioning off. To prevent these possible outcomes and to preserve the digital dignity of the deceased, some families may create memorialized pages and profiles on social media platforms, while others may opt for virtual graves. Some may even take proactive measures and pen digital wills that contain all the passwords and login information. Others may have to fight tooth and nail to retrieve the data of their loved one from the clutches of “category kings” such as Facebook or Google (McDonald and Krach, 2020), who have become the de facto stewards of the deceased’s digital remains. Naturally, these category kings tend to win court cases because the non-transferability of this data was clearly outlined in the terms and conditions. In fact, terms and conditions remain the most valid current legal mandate in the protection of the privacy and dignity of digital remains; however, the problem is that no one reads them (Fiesler et al., 2016; Mai, 2016; Obar & Oeldorf-Hirsch, 2020; Wu, 2019).

This one sided tug-of-war over the data of the dead is becoming widely recognized as internet users continue to die and leave behind masses of informational bodies (Öhman & Floridi, 2018). These informational bodies are left to decompose out in the public cyberworld where they are vulnerable and more likely to be susceptible to acts of indignation and exploitation. While the dead are not aware of the limitless offences that can occur to their data, the bereaved families, and communities they leave behind are confronted with the emotional burden of witnessing these indignities and often left feeling helpless in the face of them. Eventually, with enough rallying cries for change, the association of human dignity and the rights to informational privacy will be recognized and will facilitate the development of policies and practices that foreground and protect the dignity of the dead online.

CONCLUSION

Although the right to keep private the data that matters to us is recognized and legislations exist to protect this right, these legislations imply that the individual is very much alive. And while we would expect that the right to privacy and digital dignity would continue to shield individuals when they die, the reality is that the informational privacy of a deceased person is not inviolable. The unique contribution of this work to the field of information privacy is demonstrated in its amplification for the necessity for critical social and legal norms for guidance pertaining to the presence of digital remains and the digital death industry. In the absence of transparent social, ethical, and legal regulations, the faceless corporations that have arbitrarily become the de facto stewards of digital remains will ultimately decide the fate of how the deceased will be remembered and preserved online.

It is apparent that we are being visited more often by the digital ghosts of the dead. Like mediums and Ouija boards, the technologies of our contemporary age offer opportunities for two-way communications with the deceased. The difference now, however, is that with digital remains, we can utilize tools like social media platforms, virtual reality, or holograms and CGI to summon the dead. They return to the spaces and places they once inhabited. Their essence is once again felt when we see them on screen; hear their voices; or reach for our phones to read their messages. In difficult moments of overwhelming grief, the digital spaces of our loved ones become our refuge. Their remains remain—online *and* offline—no matter where they may be.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to express my deep gratitude to Dr. Heather O'Brien and Dr. Jennifer Douglas, my research supervisors, and Dr. Luanne Sinnamon, my committee member, for their guidance, encouragement, insights, and constructive recommendations of this research work.

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